

Agenda for Research Trends in Digital Marketing: A Conceptual Framework and its Review

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Abstract:- It is to describe and develop a conceptual framework for research in trends in digital marketing that showcase the key points in the process of marketing as well as in the marketing strategy process where digital upbringing technologies are having and will have a revelatory impact. Using the framework we are organizing the development and surviving research all around the elements and touch points that comprise the framework and review that the research literature in its widely defined digital space marketing. We are outlining the evolving issues and in around the key points and the associated questions for the future research. Finally, we are integrating these identified questions and try to set a research agenda for future research in trend of digital marketing for the examination of the issues from the perception of the firm.

I. INTRODUCTION

It has been nearly a period of time since the commercial use of Internet and the (WWW) World Wide Web has begun. During this duration the business landscape brought changes at many feverish pace .Largely multinational corporation such as Google, Instagram, myntra, Flipcart, paytm and Facebook, unheard of past twenty years ago, have emerged as important players in our economy with modern concept . Moreover, the digital technologies and such devices that are touch phones, smart products, the (IOT) Internet of Things, Artificial Intelligence, and the deep learning for all promisingly significant transformations those are of the consumers' livings to have in the upcoming future. In 2015, the online sales was accounted for 7.4% of the overall retail spending in the (U.S) united states the high percentage(%) since the tracking was began in1999 (Philips,2015). The sales made by using mobile devices that have increased to a rapid rate from between 22% and 27% of all the online sales (Malcolm, 2015). The corporation now highlights the uniqueness of creating “digital relationship” with the customers (Philips, 2015). As it was against the backdrop that this paper will seeks to guide and tries to communicate that how are the developments of digital technology are re-shaping the process including the strategy of marketing, those of its implications which results in the transformation for research process in the broaden sense as it is known as “digital marketing”.

Our prime objectives for this research paper are three-folded. First, we are developing and describing a framework for the research in the area of digital marketing that are highlighting the key points in the process of marketing as well as in the strategy process of marketing where digital technologies will have a significant impact. Then, next we are organizing the developments and extent research around those elements and key points which are comprising the framework and reviewing the literature of research in the broadly defined digital marketing area. By using this framework, we are also outlining the evolving related issues around the key points and are associated with questions for the future research. Finally, we are integrating these identified questions and are all set for a research agenda for the upcoming future research in digital and modern marketing.

In our discourse, we are examining the research related issues in digital marketing from the perspective of the firm – for which we are examining, the strategic, tactical and implementation implications for the research conducted in from the domain of digital and modern marketing which focus on the substantial issues for managerial relevance that from behavioral or methodological research per search. However, these are issues which could lead to the fundamental questions to be answered in these domains for the consumer psychology, marketing analytics, economics, or in computers. In order as to be comprehensive as soon as possible in covering all the key substantial research developments in the area of digital marketing, that are given more focus, that we have narrow down the search without compromising with the representativeness. Our basic search for the relevant literatures which focuses on the four marketing journals i.e., *The International Journal for Research in Marketing*, *Marketing Sciences*, *The Journal of Marketing Research*, and *The Journal of Marketing*, those are focusing on articles that are published between 2000 to 2016. We started the Web of Sciences and search for the article with some of the keyword “digital” or “online” as either that the research topics or the part of the articles titled, which provides us with 305 “seeds article”. As we have read those papers, we eliminate those that are not directly relevant and are included with other relevant papers cited in these seeds paper. This expands our list to that of other journals which are not covered in our initial hunt for search. For each of the topic discussed in our paper, we have to select the earliest paper in the list, and to add a few most frequently used papers in that topic to be discussed under

each of the topic making up for our reviews. To these lists we also add the most recent paper to be rendered for the reviews as soon as possible. Therefore, these reviews extend the research that is not meant to be exhaustible but rather represents in order to cover all the issues with maximum sufficient depths and with focus on future researches issues appropriately.

Our reviews complement recent review articles on digital marketing and related topics. The articles written by Pavlou (2014) focus on marketing in computer-mediated environment and reviews literatures in both the marketing and the information systems. These article by Lamberton and Stephen (2016) focus on consumers psychology, motivation, and expression in digital terms of environment to showcase a few. The article by Wedel (2016) focus on the modeling and methodology issue in the marketing analytics that necessitated by this advent of digitally, socially and from mobile environments. Our reviews quoted for these articles at the appropriate sections for further details on all issues we don't cover.

The paper is organized in such manner. In Section 2 we present the framework and identify key points in processes where digital technologies play a key role. In 3 Digital environment, 4 Marketing actions, 5 Marketing outcomes, 6 Marketing research, 7 Marketing strategy, we review the literature around each element and key point of the framework and discuss briefly open areas of inquiry. In Section 8 we present more details on these open areas of research and present an agenda for future research and conclude in Section 9.

II. SECTION SNIPPETS

➤ *Definition and framework*

This term of “digital marketing” was evolved over the time from a particular term which describes the overall marketing of product and service that are using the digital channels – to an significant term describes the process of using all digital technologies for acquiring the customer and builds customer preference, promotes brand, retains customer and increases sale (At Financial Times). Following are the (AMA) American Marketing Association's firm centric definitions.

➤ *Digitally enhanced environment*

Table 1 provides an overview of the state-of-the-art research developments under each of the five main areas we focus on.

III. PRODUCT

The concept of this product are undergoing with a fast transformations in the age of digitalization. First, of all the augmentations of all the core products with service are becoming increasing digitally, wherein its core value of the products is increased at the value that is derived from the

digital enhancement (e.g., automobile with GPS system- self-driven technology). Secondly, the networking's of product using the online and mobile technology is generating a settlement economy wherein the dormant values of own-product (e.g.)

➤ *Market outcomes*

The outcomes of the firms' actions acts as a function of the environment as they operate in that can be classified into the value for the customers encompassing of the dimensions of the value equity (the objective and the value they derive), brand equity, relationship equity (Rust and Narayan Das, 2004) and the customer satisfaction, plus customer value and all its elements, and the firm value and its elements. Much of the extant research discussed in this paper affects one or more of the above dimensions and we do not repeat all

➤ *Market research*

Digital environment serves a vast array of the data ranging and arranging from main stream data, plus customer reviews and ratings, blogs, subscriptions, tags, and other social interaction data, to the customer responses to needed marketing actions and the important information on collaborators and competitors. This collected data is very knowledgeable for all firms to understand the online customer behaviors, and to develop all marketing strategies, and to measure the effectiveness of all its actions and some tactics on marketing outcomes. In this particular section, we will focus on the empirical research that is as follows.

➤ *Market strategy*

The two core market elements that a firm can focus on it to maintain a substantial competitive advantage that is its brand and for its customers. In this part of study, we will focus on all the recent researches related to all these elements of the marketing strategies that cannot be specifically captured in all the other sections –and addresses how the firm can strategically manage its entire brand and its customers in the ever-changing digital landscapes. The introductions for all new channels, and new customer interaction calls for such

IV. AGENDA FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

By designing, our review of extant work that is in digital marketing which has its sole focus only on the marketing journals, to primarily keep the reviews traceable as well as to uncover all the gaps that exists in all the marketing literature and suggests some new topic for exploration. All new researched efforts has to be cognizant for all the theories and kind of models develop in market as well as that in consumer psychologies, sociologies, economics, computer sciences and operation research in all aspects of taking on the new lines of inquiry. From this perspective, we

V. CONCLUSION

Our main objectives in this paper are to set an agenda for researches in digital market. We have tried to define digital market in the broader sense and similarly we developed and propose frameworks that highlight the key point in the market process as well as in all the marketing strategies process where the digital technology plays an important role. By using this kind of framework we tried to organize and review the extant research all around these main points. These unresolved question in every area we tried to identifies above.

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